

***Halapricum desulfuricans* sp. nov., carbohydrate-utilizing sulfur-respiring haloarchaea from hypersaline lakes**

Dimitry Y. Sorokin, Mikhail Yakimov, Enzo Messina, Alexander Y. Merkel, Michel Koenen, Nicole J. Bale, Jaap S. Sinninghe Damsté

Supplementary Data

Table S1: Genome statistics of carbohydrate-utilizing sulfur-reducing haloarchaea.

Table S2. Intact polar lipids identified and their abundance (in percent of lipid peak area) in the carbohydrate-utilizing haloarchaea and the type species of the genus *Halapricum*: **1** - strain HSR12-1; **2** - strain HSR12- 2^T, **3** - *H. salinum*. Δ mmu = (measured mass – calculated mass) x 1000; AEC = assigned elemental composition; PGP-Me = phosphatidylglycerolphosphate methyl ester; PG = phosphatidylglycerol; MGE - glycosyl monoether; DGDE - diglycosyl diether; AR = archaeol (C₂₀-C₂₀); EXT-AR = extended archaeol (C₂₀-C₂₅); lyso = one alkyl chain is absent; uns = unsaturated; nd - not detectable

Table S3. Respiratory lipoquinones identified in three strains of the carbohydrate-utilizing sulfur-reducing haloarchaea. MMK - methylmenaquinones ("thermoplasma" quinones) **Table**

S4: Full genome comparison indexes of carbohydrate-utilizing sulfur-reducing haloarchaea and their closest related genera.

Fig. S1. Phylogenetic position of carbohydrate-utilizing sulfur-reducing haloarchaea *Halapricum desulfuricum* within the family *Haloarculaceae* based on the 16S rRNA gene sequence comparison. Bootstrap consensus tree is shown with values above 50% placed at the nodes. Bar, 0.1 changes per position.

Figure S2. Induction of sulfur- and sulfoxide-reducing activities in washed cells of carbohydrate-utilizing sulfur-reducing haloarchaeon HSR12-1 grown anaerobically with glucose and various electron acceptors. The activity was tested with either glucose or H₂ as the *e*-donors and four *e*-acceptors: sulfur, methionine sulfoxide (MSO), dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) and tetrathmethylene sulfoxide (TMSO). The cells were incubated in 4 M NaCl/50 mM K-P buffer (pH 7) at 37°C.

Supplementary **Table S1.**

Paprameter	HSR12-2 ^T	HSR12-1	HSR-Bgl	HSR-Est
Genome composition	1 chromosome	1 chromosome	1 chromosome 1 plasmid	1 chromosome 1 plasmid
Chromosome size	2,893,909 bp	2,940,338 bp	2,940,228 bp	2,699,657 bp
GC content	64.0%	64.7%	64.2%	63.6%
Total genes	3,078	3,109	3,021	2,755
rRNA genes (5S-16S-23S)	6 (2 operons) dissimilar	6 (2 operons) dissimilar	6 (2 operons) dissimilar	6 (2 operons) dissimilar
Protein-coding genes	3,024	3,055	2,968	2,701
CRISPR regions	2	2	2	-
Plasmid (size)	-	-	137,790 bp	180,725 bp
G+ C mol%	-	-	57.0	56.2
Protein-coding genes	-	-	149	158
Total number of glycosidase genes	21	17	20	26
GH13 family extracellular amylase genes	0	0	0	4

Table S2. Intact polar lipids identified and their abundance (in percent of lipid peak area) in carbohydrate-utilizing haloarchaea grown anaerobically with sulfur and glucose at 37°C and 4 M NaCl until late exponential growth phase : **1** - strain HSR12-1; **2** - strain HSR12-2^T; **3** - *Halapricum salinum* JCM 19729^T

Polar headgroup	Core	[M+NH ₄] ⁺	[M+H] ⁺	AEC	Δ mmu	Abundance (%)			
						1	2	3	
PGP-Me	EXT-AR		971.7449	C ₅₂ H ₁₀₉ O ₁₁ P ₂	0.9	25.4	32.1	34.1	
	Uns-EXT-AR*		969.7286	C ₅₂ H ₁₀₇ O ₁₁ P ₂	0.3	13.9	12.7	41.5	
	AR		901.6658	C ₄₇ H ₉₉ O ₁₁ P ₂	0.1	19.4	27.3	8.5	
	Lyso-EXT-AR		691.4316	C ₃₂ H ₆₉ O ₁₁ P ₂	0.6	0.0	0.1	0.3	
	Lyso-AR		621.3532	C ₂₇ H ₅₉ O ₁₁ P ₂	0.4	0.0	0.2	0.1	
Total						59	72	85	
PG	EXT-AR		877.7623	C ₅₁ H ₁₀₆ O ₈ P	0.3	0.4	8.8	5.7	
	Uns-EXT-AR*		875.7461	C ₅₁ H ₁₀₄ O ₈ P	0.2	0.2	4.7	2.8	
	AR		807.6837	C ₄₆ H ₉₆ O ₈ P	0.0	0.0	9.5	0.7	
	Lyso-AR		527.3704	C ₂₆ H ₅₆ O ₈ P	0.3	0.1	0.6	0.8	
	Total						1	24	10
DG	EXT-AR	1064.8926		C ₆₀ H ₁₂₂ NO ₁₃	1.5	6.9	0.7	0.5	
	Uns-EXT-AR*	1062.8763		C ₆₀ H ₁₂₀ NO ₁₃	0.9	6.0	0.5	0.6	
	AR	994.8124		C ₅₅ H ₁₁₂ NO ₁₃	0.4	5.1	1.2	0.1	
	Uns(1)-AR	992.7982		C ₅₅ H ₁₁₀ NO ₁₃	1.1	1.4	0.0	0.0	
	Total						19	2	1
MG	EXT-AR	902.8386		C ₅₄ H ₁₁₂ NO ₈	0.4	7.1	0.6	1.4	
	Uns-EXT-AR*	900.8231		C ₅₄ H ₁₁₀ NO ₈	0.5	3.9	0.4	2.3	
	AR	832.7605		C ₄₉ H ₁₀₂ NO ₈	0.5	6.9	0.7	0.7	
	Total						18	2	4
	PA	EXT-AR	803.7253		C ₄₈ H ₁₀₀ O ₆ P	0.1	1.5	nd	nd
AR		733.6475		C ₄₃ H ₉₀ O ₆ P	0.5	1.8	nd	nd	
Total							3	nd	nd
Sum AR						33	39	10	
Sum EXT-AR						41	42	42	
Sum uns-AR						0	1	1	
Sum uns-EXT-AR						0	0	0	
Sum lyso-AR						1	0	0	
Sum lyso-EXT-AR						24	18	47	

Δ mmu = (measured mass – calculated mass) x 1000 as calculated for strain 1; AEC = assigned elemental composition; PGP-Me = phosphatidylglycerolphosphate methyl ester; PG = phosphatidylglycerol; PA = phosphatidic acid; MG = monoglycosyl; DG = diglycosyl; AR = archaeol (C₂₀-C₂₀); EXT-AR = extended archaeol (C₂₀-C₂₅); lyso = one alkyl chain is absent; uns = unsaturated. *Sum of species with 1-4 unsaturations, mass given for species with one unsaturation. nd = not detected.

Table S3. Menaquinones identified in carbohydrate-utilizing haloarchaea.**1** - strain HSR12-1; **2** - strain HSR12-2^T; **3** - *Halapricum salinum* JCM 19729^T

Core	[M+H] ⁺	AEC	Δ mmu	Abundance (%)		
				1	2	3
MK-8:8	717.5615	C ₅₁ H ₇₃ O ₂	1.0	36.1	16.7	12.9
MK-8:7	719.5772	C ₅₁ H ₇₅ O ₂	1.0	55.5	61.4	68.0
MK-7:7	649.4987	C ₄₆ H ₆₅ O ₂	0.8	1.4	0.8	0.2
MK-7:6	651.5143	C ₄₆ H ₆₇ O ₂	0.8	1.9	2.0	0.9
Total				94.9	80.9	100
MMK-8:8	731.5773	C ₅₂ H ₇₅ O ₂	1.1	2.5	3.3	nd
MMK-8:7	733.5924	C ₅₂ H ₇₇ O ₂	0.6	2.6	15.8	nd
Total				5.1	19.1	nd

MMK - methylmenaquinones ("thermoplasma" quinones). Δ mmu = (measured mass – calculated mass) x 1000 as calculated for strain 1; AEC = assigned elemental composition. nd = not detected.

Table S4.

Index	HSR-Bgl	HSR-Est	HSR12-1	HSR12-2 ^T	CBA1105 ^T
ANib					
HSR-Bgl	*	83.45 [58.29]	92.79 [72.59]	97.82 [82.67]	77.58 [48.65]
HSR-Est	83.57 [62.10]	*	83.57 [64.51]	83.74 [62.89]	77.45 [52.62]
HSR12-1	93.10 [71.99]	83.56 [60.13]	*	93.03 [71.62]	77.50 [48.56]
HSR12-2 ^T	98.01 [84.12]	83.71 [59.15]	92.98 [72.33]	*	77.69 [46.61]
<i>Halapricum salinum</i> CBA1105 ^T	77.37 [41.18]	77.08 [42.07]	77.50 [41.15]	77.54 [39.54]	*
ANIm					
HSR-Bgl	*	86.98 [51.42]	93.76 [77.64]	98.39 [86.11]	84.51 [24.40]
HSR-Est	86.96 [55.52]	*	87.12 [57.40]	87.18 [56.11]	84.36 [26.44]
HSR12-1	93.75 [77.49]	87.12 [52.66]	*	93.72 [76.83]	84.54 [24.81]
HSR12-2 ^T	98.36 [87.67]	87.19 [52.69]	93.72 [78.16]	*	84.54 [24.90]
<i>Halapricum salinum</i> CBA1105 ^T	84.50 [20.48]	84.37 [20.45]	84.54 [20.82]	84.54 [20.44]	*
AAI (Two-way) [SD] percentage					
HSR-Bgl	*	82.89 [12.86]	92.81 [10.85]	97.60 [7.99]	73.21 [15.16]
HSR-Est	82.89 [12.86]	*	83.34 [12.39]	83.35 [12.47]	73.50 [15.08]
HSR12-1	92.81 [10.85]	83.34 [12.39]	*	93.12 [9.95]	73.23 [15.09]
HSR12-2 ^T	97.60 [7.99]	83.35 [12.47]	93.12 [9.95]	*	73.28 [15.41]
<i>Halapricum salinum</i> CBA1105 ^T	73.21 [15.16]	73.50 [15.08]	73.23 [15.09]	73.28 [15.41]	*
GGDC (DDH formula 2)					
	[p(DDH)>70%]	[same species]			
HSR-Bgl	*	28.30	53.00	85.10 [93.79]	19.20
HSR-Est	28.30	*	28.50	28.80	22.40
HSR12-1	53.00	28.50	*	52.80	23.00
HSR12-2 ^T	85.10 [93.79]	28.80	52.80	*	22.90
<i>Halapricum salinum</i> CBA1105 ^T	19.20	22.40	23.00	22.90	*

Supplementary Fig. S1

Supplementary Fig. S2